

“E-Banking”

K.Bhavani

Mount Carmel College (Autonomous), Bengaluru

T.R.Chaitra

Mount Carmel College (Autonomous), Bengaluru

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Abstract

As an aid for the advancement of the digitalized country, in India all the businesses are moving towards the Electronic Media to cope-up with the digitalization. E-Banking is one among those which is switching over the electronic mode that is making the service reach the customers in less time with not much of effort. But yet the customers are not prepared to rely on such improvisation as there is a lot of measures, yet to be taken up for the sector to work on its security level and educating the customer for the utilization of such revolution. The age-old paper work of the transaction process into the electronic gadgets can be smartly coined as E-Banking. Here in the conclusion of our survey, we are heading in finding the varied perception about the renovation in E- Banking.

Keywords: Finance Industry, E-developments, Renovations, Perception

Objectives

- To identify the customer’s perception about the E-Banking
- How far the objective of the transformation is achieved.

Methodology

This study employs a quantitative approach that uses closed - ended framework of research design. The basic aim of the research is to conduct a survey on the general public, in order to understand E-Banking in their perception. To understand the views of people the survey is conducted online and the questionnaire consists of 10 questions which are closed ended and the same is studied, analysed, founded and concluded. Survey is conducted with a Sample size of “**60 respondents**” by using Scaling technique of measurement. The sample are drawn in such a way that there are 20 people from youths/ students’ group and 40 people from working group. The sample design used in this survey is Convenience Sample Design, as the samples are drawn as per our convenience.

Analysis of Data

- Questionnaire – Online survey with 10 questions with sample size as 60 respondents
- Analysis and Calculations – Analysed using Measurement of Scaling Technique
- On the basis of Youth/Students – 20 i.e. (33.33%)
- On the basis of working group – 40 i.e. (66.67%)

Findings

- 58% of the sample chooses online banking service for Convenience.
- 47% of the sample use online services in the frequency of Monthly.
- 49% of the sample use transfer funds as their regular online function.
- 72% of the sample uses their mobile phone for banking.
- 31% of the sample uses mobile banking for Utility bill payments and 28% of them use balance enquiry.
- 55% of the sample visit branches in spite of using online banking.
- 68% of the sample is satisfied with online banking service.
- 38% of the sample does not use online banking for the reason as they don't trust on internet service and 26% for no internet access.
- 43% of the sample doesn't trust or in the state of dilemma with regard to banks that only operate online.
- 46% of the sample completely thinks and 48% are in the state of dilemma that human contact is important for banking relation.

Suggestions

- Banks should take necessary steps to create awareness about the advantages of e-banking / internet banking services.
- Because the customers presume internet channels are complicate they do not avail the e-banking services hence banks may set up a team of personnel to train the customers.
- Banks should come up with various applications which provide security to the users of online banking.

- On-site training can be provided to the bank customers who intend to use e-banking / internet banking services.

Limitations

- Since the sample taken is small number, we cannot apply the study at a larger scale. The results may vary when applied at a larger sample.
- Time was a limiting factor to this research.
- The study was conducted using an online survey. However, we feel that a personal interview would have fetched a more realistic opinion.

Conclusion

The customers are lacking back in the knowledge of availing the services of Internet Banking or E-banking, even though this makes the customer convenient in availing the services.

The main consequences caused to the customer are mainly concerned with security issues and the complications that are raised through internet. In return if bank tries to take measure in educating the customers and sorting the trust issues the industry can achieve their objective of introducing E-way to provide the services.

By taking up these necessary actions the finance industry that is renovating and merging to the e-developments can be enhanced and this is partly in relation with the path of making the Indian Economy into Digitalization.